

COGNITIVE AND COMMUNICATIVE ASPECTS OF REPRESENTATION OF STYLISTIC DEVICES IN ADVERTISING SLOGANS

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Abstract: The objective of the article is to provide the analysis of language of advertising from linguistic point of view and specify linguistic means used in advertising texts. The article supports the analysis of language of advertising from linguistic point of view and specifies linguistic means used in advertising texts. The article gives knowledge about the use of linguistic devices in advertising. By analytical method, author tried to find out the use of rate of individual linguistic means used in advertising slogans. Even in relation to product specialization.

Keywords: Advertising slogans, language of advertising, linguistic devices.

Introduction. Advertising has become the part and band of present day life. From everywhere around us, advertisements of different types attack our privacy. In spite of it, there's an attractive power, which is able to manipulate the consumer, an invisible voice of advertisement supporters, encourages, asks, announces and deeply embeds into people's minds.

In the last decades, the market an excessive quantity of advertising caused the increased intention and interest in linguistic aspect of advertising.

Advertising has become a science. People began to describe, analyze the linguistic means and estimate the language trying to find out the principles, create new kinds of connection between elements of language and improve the approaches,

with the aim to be unique and maximize the effect at full blast. Linguistics are interested in language of advertising because they desire know how particular language works in this type of discourse. English advertising capitalize on the high adaptability of the English language. English allows the creators of advertisements to use word puns, linguistic devices such as metaphor, anaphora, metonymy, figurative language and to mix individual styles and types of texts. Advertising unifies language, pictures, music: it consists of information, invokes emotions and imaginations.

Different puns or equivoques which present "a figure of speech which indicates a play upon words " are famous among copywriters due to the element of surprise they bring along and several possible interpretations .

Epithets are used to make the products description more vivid and enticing:

" Life has never been so colorful" (SONY)

Ellipses is a syntactical scheme when one or more words are omitted" It is very typical of advertising. Examples of ellipses can be found in the following slogans:

L'oreal " Because you are worth it"

Nespresso "Nespresso, what else?"

Interrogative sentence types are often presented in a form of rhetorical question, which is essentially a question not expecting an answer, or one to which the answer is more or less self-evident .

Ford "Have you driven a Ford lately?"

Wendy's "Where is the beef?"

Every day, people are exposed to tens of thousands of advertisements, making it impossible for them to recall them all. Most of the time, people simply disregard the messages they are exposed to. Marketers are forced to develop ads because

consumers are becoming more sophisticated, picky, and resistant to being convinced. Much more attention-grabbing and memorable. Ad campaign catchphrases are a clever way to achieve this. Successful advertising campaigns require memorable slogans. Catchy advertising slogans have been used by both large and small enterprises. The definition of the advertising slogan in scientific literature varies depending on the author, taking into account different aspects of the phrase or simply listing synonyms.

Dowling and Kabanoff, who define advertising slogans as a few words that "appear beneath or beside the corporate name at the bottom of a print advertisement and are separated from the body copy for easy recognition," also support the notion that the slogan is a tool that aids a customer in recognizing the brand. These scholars contend that the advertising slogan not only serves as a reminder of the brand or business, but also is memorable in and of itself. Similar to this, Smetonien claims in her study that slogans for advertisements might aid in memorization of the advertisement itself since "they remind of and consolidate ideas offered in the introduction" or "clearly represent the core idea of the advertisement."

Many authors define the advertising slogan while taking into account its unique qualities, or they may only list its synonyms. Although there isn't a single definition in the scientific literature that encompasses all the qualities and purposes of the advertising slogan, all the descriptions listed above have something in common. Therefore, we would describe an advertising slogan as a succinct, memorable phrase associated with a particular brand that sums up, communicates, and aids consumers in recalling the main ideas of a brand or advertising campaign.

During the examination, metaphor was found in a number of commercial slogans. By comparing one thing to another, typically implicitly, metaphor enhances the aesthetics of the message and accentuates the core concept. When two seemingly unconnected objects are contrasted using a metaphor, it helps to identify the parallels

or connections that would otherwise go unnoticed by declaring that one is the same as the other:

- Fresh Squeezed Glaciers (Adelma Mineral Water)
- It just feels right to hold the internet in your hands (Apple iPad)
- Bounty- the taste of paradise (Bounty candy bar)
- Open Happiness (Coca Cola)
- Put a tiger in your tank (Esso)
- It gives you wings (Red Bull)

Due to their reliance on lexical terms with many meanings, advertisers frequently employ puns or word games; occasionally, word games involve homophones or homonyms. Although Leech claims that in advertising language ambiguity "hinges on the spelling rather than on pronunciation," the pun or word play is founded on ambiguity (Leech, 1972, 184). Puns, according to Ding (2003), "may fascinate and impress the public with its smartness and its freshness," which "can perform miracles" when used in advertising slogans to help establish brand identification.

The act of imitating or embodying a quality or abstraction, or the attribution of human characteristics to inanimate objects, is known as personification. Personification occurs naturally in many languages when gender is used (Cuddon, 1999, 661). Advertising frequently employs personification, the imbuing of inanimate objects or abstractions with human characteristics, in order to increase drama, intrigue, and appeal since personified items are easier for us to relate to.

The first cream that renews your skin during the night (Nivea)

Several of the slogans in the examined advertisements make use of the figurative language technique known as the apostrophe, which "addresses a thing, a location,

an abstract characteristic, a concept, a dead or absent person, as if present and capable of comprehending" (Cuddon, 1999, 51).

- Finger lickin' good (KFC)
- I'm lovin' it (MacDonalds's)
- You've never seen "Bodie's" like this! (Victoria Secret)
- Where's the beef? (Wendy's)

Conclusion. Although every definition of an advertising slogan differs from author to author, they all agree that an advertising slogan is a succinct, memorable phrase that is associated with a particular brand and that defines, presents, and aids consumers in remembering the key ideas of a brand or advertising campaign. The analysis showed that sound techniques were employed in 32% of the slogans, figurative language was utilized in 40% of the selected slogans, and other rhetorical devices were used in 28% of the slogans (repetition, comparison, parallelism, antithesis, and hyperbole). The use of pun (word play) is present in 16% of the sampled English advertising slogans, while simile, personification, and paradox are the least common.

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